

The Usage of 'Let Go Vandalism' Intervention in Curbing Vandalism Behaviour among Year Five Pupils

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Abstract: This study aims to identify factors causing vandalism and intervention to reduce vandalism among year five students of Primary School Simpang Lima 1 Klang. Vandalism is a major problem faced by educators in schools. Among those involved in vandalime like intimidation, destroying school possessions and bullying. This action study uses quantitative approach with descriptive type design to obtain feedback from samples. The instrument of study used is a questionnaire. This study involved eight respondents selected from the year fivestudents from the school students personality System (SSDM). The study shows that a total of eight male pupils comprising Indians and Chinese are most dominant to do vandalism in the school. This study was conducted for four months on students who did vandalism. Based on the findings of research, indicating that factors that contribute to the formation of vandalism are caused by the negative influence of peers. Based on initial findings, a intervention programme is implemented to reduce problems in this school through "let go vandalism" (LGV) interventions involving several activities. There are five intervention programmes to be carried out through group activities and individual activities together with the students of vandalism. Among the interventions conducted are 'why we are here', 'psychodrama wipe out vandalism', 'treasure', 'motivation to myself', and 'create dreams'. The main factor for the intervention programme is to provide awareness among the year five pupils. The implications of this study found that interventions helped pupils increase self-awareness on offences committed. Several suggestions such as external party collaboration such as police, authorities, community and the support of parents are necessary to prevent the behavior of vandalism from continuing to be prevalent in school.

Keywords: vandalism, behaviour, pupils, peers, intervention

I. Introduction

Students are one of the various social problems that have been spreading nowadays. (Sri Wahyuni, RB. Soemanto, Nice Haryono, 2015). Social symptoms among the students in this country become a threat to the local community's peace and harmony and environment. Behavior, all human action that can be watched, measured and evaluated and any acts done either directly or indirectly, be aware or partially aware (Mohammad Faizal Zakri, 2012).

The study of vandalism was largely carried out by previous researchers and according to the earlier studies found that teenagers dominated the social symptoms and are seen as much of the catch-up rates of growing the day. According to Zakaria Stapa, 2012, social environmental factors could have impacted a reaction to the creation of a person's behavior and self-esteem. While other studies say the cooperation of the elderly, parents with teachers is a communication relationship in developing students development and able to solve students problems in the school. (H. Syarif Hidayat, (2013). A variety of main cause factors that bring

students to the path are incorrect. Among them are self-factors, family backgrounds, parenting and the school's parents. (Mohamad, Haji Othman, (2016).

Vandalism or habit of damaging public property is the worst habit that occurs in most schools in Malaysia. Researchers have made surveys in the study area and are found to have a similar conduct of the walls and signs using pencils, marker and paint are among the main vandalism that students do. There are also teenagers who love using foot shoes and mud to staining the walls of idle houses, shops and so on. In addition, teenagers are also involved in damaging the toilet pumps, extracting pipes, damaging sinks, public phones, playground and many more.

This study aims to identify and reduce social problems which are vandalism among the pupils of SK 1 Simpang Lima Klang. This study of action is important to open the eyes of society especially parents and teachers, especially counselling teachers. The school always strives to overcome social problems and increase the academic achievement of school pupils.

According to the *Third edition action Survey Manual booklet (2008)*, the target group refers to a group of teachers or students involved in a study that will be conducted. The teachers ' groups or pupils must be the group involved in issues of research problems and social-related situations. The study was conducted to 8 male pupils comprising 6 Indians, and 2 Chinese aged 11. Students were selected through the student's self-personality system (SSDM). The school needs to make improvements so that the problem of vandalism should be reduced. Therefore, a study should be implemented to solve this problem so that the school can reduce the problem of disciplinary through in future. There are two key factors to be identified as family and peer factors. Researchers would like to see if there is a relationship between these factors and the behaviors of vandalism among students and some of the factors that cause vandalism.

II. Research Objectives

This study was conducted to achieve the following objectives:

- i. To identify if a family factor or peer factor causes vandalism among year fivepupils in SK (1) Simpang Lima Klang.
- ii. To identify the effectiveness of intervention programmes implemented to reduce the problem of vandalism in SK 1 Simpang Lima Klang.
- iii. The Wilcoxon test shows that there is a difference before and after a pre-test and post-testing that has give a good impact on the decline of vandalism activities in school.

III. Methodology

Action studies as a method aimed at having a result of action and research outcomes. The method of action study is practical and collaborative. Therefore, the study of action is a study involving the improvement of researchers practices in reducing the problems of vandalism in the school. To see such an issue, researchers need to look at the behavior of pupils that pose a disciplinary problem. The selection method of this document is one of the important methods to obtain information or knowledge for this research assignment. Researchers use this method to obtain as many findings as possible or relevant information in connection with their title. The process of obtaining information is focused on reading and reference from books, journals, paper and articles. All information obtained will be used by researchers in writing.

This action study is a survey study to assist and guide researchers to obtain the information required in the study. The survey method is used using a set of questionnaire questions. Quantitative approach applies to obtaining data required through this study. Researchers use questionnaires and structured interviews to measure the behavior of vandalism and factors that motivate the behavior of vandalism. Questions through instruments questionnaires are used for students personal information such as age, gender, parental work, income and academic achievement of parents.

This study uses a structured question interview to obtain clear responses to the problems to be reviewed. Interviews are conducted with queries that consist of open questions. The questions in the interview are intended to enable participants to speak and share experiences and knowledge, to obtain the maximum data

needed for this study. The audio recording was performed when researchers recorded the respondent's speech to be used as primary data. During the interview, conversation between respondents and researchers was recorded. It is also used to measure the behavior of vandalism and factors that motivate the behavior.

This study was conducted through several work processes. Data collection techniques are such as in Figure1.

Figure 1:Data collection techniques

The initial data collection to identify the actual issues were obtained through questionnaires that were built with questions regarding the cause of student involvement in vandalism and also issues that cause students to act violent. A 16-year experienced counselling teacher was chosen to be a sample for this study. Questions in the questionnaire are meant to enable the respondents to share their experiences to obtain the maximum data required for this study. The respondent welcomes both the methods used and does not have any problems when answering the questionnaire.

Investigators have a good relationship with the respondent by making an appointment to 8 concurrent respondents carried out the pre test and the next question is given. A descriptive question is initiated by asking

respondents or informant to clear, register or elaborate on the variety and situation of events, experiences, places, in a college profession. The reviewer needs to make a document analysis process first such as personal document analysis, such as diaries, portrait letters or pictures, recordings, keepsakes. These documents can be used as the founder and interview guide without imposing a structure of speech against the respondent or informant.

In the beginning, researchers began with general questions in relation to demographics and others. Researchers do not continue to enter the question of study in order to give the respondent the time to prepare for this study. According to *Abu Kassim (2016)*, there were several levels of reliability, information. Researchers should treat this information with respect. Researchers do not judge or assess the respondent in negative. What is more important is to accept them what is the same.

Researchers use questionnaires and structured interviews as a research tool to collect information about the students involved in vandalism. Questions related to vandalism have been given in the form of questionnaires so that researchers can be thoroughly on the basis of the respondent. The questionnaire is an effective way to obtain information from the respondent in studying factors that contribute to vandalism

Let Go vandalism's intervention programme has given a variety of different effects and reactions among the students for each activity. These activities were taken and modified according to primary school levels from the Ministry of Education Malaysia's output. The intervention phase begins with the implementation of 5 modules by school guidance teachers in every meeting.

IV. Finding and Discussions

Families are the only social institutions that can form the behavior and be able to direct appropriate social activities according to the development of the children (*BuerahTunggak,Shanah Ngadi, Hamimah Abu Naim, 2015*). While peer is an important factor in vandalism. Young people are often more likely to be affected by peers (*IsranElnadi 2018*).According to *IsranElnadi, 2018*, that peer influences are the main factors of vandalism.This is because teenagers are usually more easily affected by peers. In addition to peers, he said that the parents were also the motivator to the nature of vandalism among pupils. While according to *RekaYanti, AlberTigorArifyanto, Abas Rudin, 2020*, supports that the cause of vandalism caused by the family environmental factors that are a major source of juvenile delinquency, the study found there are several factors that have been inflicted by the respondent's study that caused vandalism among pupils. The factors given are family factors and peer factors.

Based on the analysis of questionnaires and structured interviews answered by 8 respondents, the following table 1 shows the breakdown of respondents for the cause of the causes of vandalism in schools. This section explains the results of data analysis based on the respondent's response to a questionnaire that has been carried out on factors causing the behavior to occur.

Table 1: Demography 8 respondents based on pre-test answers

RESPONDENT	FAMILY FACTORS	PEER FACTOR
RESPONDENT1		✓
RESPONDENT 2	✓	
RESPONDENT 3		✓
RESPONDENT 4		✓
RESPONDENT 5		✓
RESPONDENT 6		✓
RESPONDENT 7	✓	
RESPONDENT 8		✓

Table 1 shows that the highest number of 7 respondents have chosen peers as a cause of vandalism in schools and only 2 respondents choose family factors as a cause of vandalism. The results of questionnaires and

structured interviews that were answered by the respondents showed that the cause factor was a peer compared to parental factors.

As mentioned by *BuerahTunggak, Shanah Ngadi, Hamimah Abu Naim, 2015*, peer is a teenager of the same age or with the same maturity level. Peer plays an important role in a teenager's life. There are various factors that can lead to this problem and the peer influences are the biggest factor. They have the same desires and enjoyment when collaborating on an activity. Their relationship is close to each other.

Peer is the most important person to teenagers, in addition to parents and family members. Peers strongly influence someone's behaviour, especially those who are having problems with family members. Teenagers who choose a peer that behave badly, some will followed with those actions. Doing criminal activities such as damaging public property or other people's property is a challenging one. If a friend is uninvolved often do that act, the most likely a student will be stuck alike. Peer has a dominant influence on youth acts in all beneficial or non-advantageous activities and this is a factor that the main cause of pupils do vandalism in SK 1 Simpang Lima Klang. Based on this outcome, a intervention programme is conducted to the students of disciplinary risk to vandalism.

Table 2: Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test

		N	Rank mean	Number's of rank
Post_Academic - Pre_Academic	Negative Ranks	0 ^a	.00	.00
	Positive Ranks	8 ^b	4.50	36.00
	Ties	0 ^c		
	Total	8		
Post_EmotionalSocial - Pre_EmotionalSocial	Negative Ranks	0 ^d	.00	.00
	Positive Ranks	8 ^e	4.50	36.00
	Ties	0 ^f		
	Total	8		

Table 2 continued

Post_family – Pre_family	Negative Ranks	0 ^g	.00	.00
	Positive Ranks	8 ^h	4.50	36.00
	Ties	0 ⁱ		
	Total	8		
PostPeers – Pre_Peers	Negative Ranks	0 ^j	.00	.00
	Positive Ranks	8 ^k	4.50	36.00
	Ties	0 ^l		
	Total	8		

Table 3: Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test

	Post Academic Pre-Academic	Post EmotionalSocial Pre-EmotionalSocial	Post Family Pre-Family	Post Peers Pre-Peers
Z	-2.521 ^b	-2.539 ^b	-2.558 ^b	-2.536 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.012	.011	.011	.011

a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

The findings in Table 2 and 3 showed that after the post test there was significant in a peer with a value of 0.011. Where, the hypothesis is null rejected and hypothesis alternative accepted. Therefore, peer is an

important factor to influence pupils to be caught in the activity of vandalism among primary school pupils with a value of 0.011. The Wilcoxon test shows that there is a difference before and after a pre-test and post-testing that has had a good impact on the decline in school activities.

V. Suggestions

Researchers want to improve the activities carried out through several suggestions as follow-up actions. In implementing this study, researchers have found that improvements can be carried out by giving responsibility to the participants such as selecting each participant as the head to guide each member in all the activities that have been carried out. Through the results of the participants in handling each activity can evaluate the success of the participants and the trust being undertaken. Upon termination of session and attitude change, pupils are given awards and appointed as 'anti-vandalism' member so that help teachers monitor and report misconduct vandalism of other pupils confidentially to coaching teachers.

The effectiveness of the intervention programme from the aspect of enhancing the respondent's attitude with five activities has given positive feedback. During the third activity, researchers can see the positive thinking of the respondent through the answers given. Researchers want to improve for the activities carried out through individual and cluster sessions. There are also few pupils who are absent from the intervention program and the pupils will be monitored weekly through the group's guidance by counseling

In addition, participants must be given a stimulus by giving gifts or tokens while attending to counselling sessions each time voluntarily. Gift grants such as full attendance certificate for each activity and also during the upcoming counselling sessions can stimulate participants to participate in each activity without skipping it. In fact, class teachers and discipline teachers have to supervise the pupils and provide good reviews in the practice of SSDM and provide the Best Personality award certificate during the Day of Excellence at the school. These students need to always provide responsibility as a leader in every activity conducted in school so that they are not ignored and are focused on them. This will inspire them that they are loved and appreciated by all parties.

VI. Conclusion

Based on findings of study, vandalism can be minimized if they are always being trained or monitored. Based on this mentioned aspect, the roles and responsibilities of teachers as an educator are enormous and demanded in helping to curb social problems from occurring and spreading. The high commitment and commitment in carrying out social symptoms of the students are demanded to be claimed for students who are born to become people contributing to outstanding human capital.

Findings of study have shown that all targeted objectives have been achieved. The findings have also shown that the intervention programme which has been implemented showed good results with the reduction of disciplinary problems in the school SSDM. Education at all levels is hoped to increase awareness of the public property as well as other. All parties must cooperate in addressing this problem so that vandalism symptoms do not continue to spread into the youth organization, thus producing good and ethical youths in their lives.

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